

ACUTE ABDOMEN IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: Acute abdomen in children is a serious medical condition that requires prompt evaluation and treatment. It refers to the sudden onset of severe abdominal pain, which can be caused by a variety of underlying conditions such as appendicitis, bowel obstruction, or intussusception. The article describes the main causes of acute abdomen in children, their course, and emergency assistance.

Keywords: Acute abdomen in children, evaluation and treatment, fever, and nausea, appendix.

Acute abdomen in children is a serious medical condition that requires prompt evaluation and treatment. It refers to the sudden onset of severe abdominal pain, which can be caused by a variety of underlying conditions such as appendicitis, bowel obstruction, or intussusception.

One of the most common causes of acute abdomen in children is appendicitis, which is the inflammation of the appendix. This condition typically presents with pain in the right lower quadrant of the abdomen, fever, and nausea. Prompt surgical intervention is often required to remove the inflamed appendix and prevent complications such as perforation and peritonitis.

Bowel obstruction is another common cause of acute abdomen in children, which can be caused by a variety of factors such as hernias, intussusception, or adhesions. Symptoms of bowel obstruction include severe abdominal pain, bloating, vomiting, and constipation. Treatment may involve surgery to remove the obstruction and restore normal bowel function.

Intussusception is a **medical emergency** that occurs when one segment of the intestine telescopes into another, causing a blockage. Children with intussusception typically present with sudden onset of severe abdominal pain, vomiting, and "currant jelly" stools. Prompt diagnosis and treatment with an air

or barium enema are essential to reduce the risk of bowel necrosis and perforation.

Other causes of acute abdomen in children include gastroenteritis, pancreatitis, and ovarian torsion. Healthcare providers need to perform a thorough physical examination, obtain a detailed medical history, and order appropriate diagnostic tests such as blood work, imaging studies, and ultrasound to determine the underlying cause of the acute abdomen.

Acute abdomen in children can have a variable course depending on the underlying cause. Prompt recognition, evaluation, and treatment are essential to prevent complications and improve outcomes. Emergency care for children with acute abdomen typically involves a systematic approach to diagnosis and management.

When a child presents with acute abdominal pain, healthcare providers will first assess the child's vital signs and perform a thorough physical examination. The presence of signs such as fever, tachycardia, and abdominal rigidity may indicate a more serious underlying condition that requires immediate intervention.

Diagnostic tests such as blood work, imaging studies (such as ultrasound or CT scan), and urinalysis may be ordered to help identify the cause of the acute abdomen. In some cases, exploratory surgery may be necessary for a definitive diagnosis and treatment.

Treatment of acute abdomen in children depends on the underlying cause. For conditions such as appendicitis or bowel obstruction, surgical intervention may be required to remove the inflamed appendix or relieve the obstruction. In cases of intussusception, non-surgical reduction with an air or barium enema may be attempted.

Pain management is an important aspect of emergency care for children with acute abdomen. Analgesics may be administered to help alleviate pain and discomfort while awaiting further evaluation and treatment.

In cases where the underlying cause of acute abdomen is unclear, close monitoring and frequent reassessment of the child's condition are necessary. Children with signs of peritonitis, sepsis, or bowel ischemia require immediate surgical consultation and intervention.

In conclusion, acute abdomen in children is a serious condition that requires prompt evaluation and treatment to prevent complications and improve outcomes. Parents should seek immediate medical attention if their child

experiences sudden onset of severe abdominal pain, as early intervention is crucial in managing these potentially life-threatening conditions.

Acute abdomen in children is a serious medical condition that requires prompt evaluation and treatment. Emergency care for children with acute abdomen involves a systematic approach to diagnosis, appropriate use of diagnostic tests, and timely intervention to prevent complications and improve outcomes. Parents should seek immediate medical attention if their child experiences sudden onset of severe abdominal pain to ensure timely and appropriate care.

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